

ISSN : 2349-4212

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF

TRENDS IN BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION

Indexed by:

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Founder and Publisher **academic journals PVT LTD**

Published science may 2011 year. Issued Quarterly.

Internet address: <http://academicjournalonline.org/index.php/ijtba>

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PRIORITY DIRECTIONS AND INDICATORS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article focuses on developing and implementing innovative projects where special attention is paid. They are expanding the possibilities of synchronization with the enterprise's strategic planning and budgeting system based on developing an effective mechanism for managing business processes. Considering resource capabilities and limitations, which allow innovative technologies to move to a new level of quality, suggestions and recommendations are given.

Keywords: Innovative Economy, Innovative Project, Innovative Technology, Innovative Process, Digital Economy, Electronic Communication, Corporate Knowledge.

I. INTRODUCTION

The research of the leading companies engaged in developing and implementing innovative projects shows that at the initial stage of the creation of innovative technologies, the design of technical and management solutions is carried out using special software. Prototypes are produced, thereby optimizing the cost structure. For this purpose, today, special technology parks are being established based on enterprises worldwide under the leadership of highly qualified specialists and developers. In this regard, the President of our republic, Sh. Mirziyoev, said: - "IT park with modern infrastructure is being built in Tashkent city. It is already showing its first results. Such IT parks will also be established in the cities of Nukus, Bukhara, Namangan, Samarkand, Gulistan and Urganch. The creation of technopark will create new jobs, and develop new technologies for enterprises - it helps to

transition to innovative development and increase competitiveness. But in some cases, due to inefficient use of innovative technologies in enterprise activity, difficulties in their content and use, problems in their perception and practical application arise. In this regard, innovative technologies, including new forms of electronic communication (Internet, voice mail, video messages, IP-telephony, etc.), the need to restructure the corporate knowledge management system and increase its quality are innovative tasks facing enterprises.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following scholars have considered priority directions and indicators of the development of innovative technologies in Uzbekistan in their research: Perez Carlota [2], Mirzaev K. [3], Ortik E., Khurshida K., Askar D. [4], Mirzaev K.J., Rahimov Z.K. [5], Kudratov G. Kh., Mirzaev K. J. [6], Mirzaev K. J. [7], Mirzaev K., Janzakov B. [8], Jamankulova F.E., Nizomov M.Q. [9], Jomonkulova F.E., Nizomov M.Q., Uralov S.A. [10], Jomonkulova F.E., Tojiyev, N.S., Nizomov M.Q., Uralov S.A. [11].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

We used logical analysis and synthesis methods, grouping, comparative and structural analysis, abstraction, factor analysis, induction and deduction in this research.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The effective use of innovative technologies in developing an innovative economy in our republic is one of the important directions of state policy. In the Address of the President of our Republic Sh. Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis in Uzbekistan, the following priority directions of the state for the development of innovative technologies were determined. Including:

- creating economic conditions for effective use of innovative technologies in our republic, “... active transition to the digital economy will be one of the most important tasks in the next 5 years¹;

- “wide implementation of digital technologies in state and community management, social sphere and increase effectiveness²” is achieved;

-“This year we need to make a radical change in the development of the digital economy. First of all, it is necessary to fully digitize the fields of construction, education, and archives³” as a result, an opportunity to develop innovative technologies in all sectors and sectors of the economy is created;

-“... It is necessary to review the electronic government system critically, implement programs and projects, and comprehensively solve all organizational and institutional issues⁴“, in this regard, effective use of innovative technologies is carried out.

-“...it is necessary to introduce information technologies that fully meet international standards at all stages of education⁵“league is defined.

- “To develop the program “Digital Uzbekistan-2030” for the rapid development of our country’s economy⁶” is set to be implemented.

- Implementation of systematic work on “fundamental improvement of their software through wide implementation of information technologies in banks...” and other similar directions are defined.

The research of the leading companies engaged in the development and implementation of innovative projects shows that at the initial stage of the creation of innovative technologies, the design of technical and management solutions is carried out using special software, then prototypes are produced, thereby optimizing

¹Mirziyoev Sh.M. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. // People's word, January 25, 2020.

²In that place.

³In that place.

⁴Mirziyoev Sh.M. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. // People's word, January 25, 2020.

⁵In that place.

⁶In that place.

the cost structure. For this purpose, today, special technology parks are being established based on enterprises around the world under the leadership of highly qualified specialists and developers. In this regard, the President of our republic, Sh. Mirziyoev said: - "IT park with modern infrastructure is being built in Tashkent city. It is already showing its first results. Such IT parks will also be established in the cities of Nukus, Bukhara, Namangan, Samarkand, Gulistan and Urganch.⁷. Creation of technopark will create new jobs and develop new technologies for enterprises - it helps to transition to innovative development and increase competitiveness. But in some cases, due to inefficient use of innovative technologies in enterprise activity, difficulties in their content and use, problems in their perception and practical application arise. In this regard, innovative technologies, including new forms of electronic communication (Internet, voice mail, video messages, IP-telephony, etc.), the need to restructure the corporate knowledge management system and increase its quality are innovative tasks facing enterprises.

Some research⁸ results show that when advanced methods of innovative technologies are used, the company radically changes its business processes, revises the business processes that harmonize the company's goals and consumer requirements, and allows adaptation to the market.

The study of innovative technologies from the point of view of orientation to the management process creates the need to search for, develop and distribute innovations as a separate process in enterprises. In this regard, it is appropriate to clearly define the goals of innovation management, responsibility distribution (process owner). The practice of innovation projects shows that the process of innovation management in Uzbek enterprises is often ineffective, resulting in a decrease in competitiveness. Therefore, for the introduction of innovative

⁷In that place.

⁸Perez, Carlota (2002). [Technological Revolutions and Financial Capital: The Dynamics of Bubbles and Golden Ages](#). UK: Edward Elgar Publishing Limited. [ISBN978-1-84376-331-4](#).

technologies in enterprises, a continuous and continuous process is required, which includes the following stages:

- search for new ideas, technological solutions;
- testing technologies in enterprise activities in a small area;
- application of innovative technology throughout the enterprise and achieving efficiency;
- assessment of profitability in using innovative technologies (based on the discount method) and the like.

It is worth noting that the use of innovative technologies creates the possibility of synchronization with the strategic planning and budgeting system of the enterprise, based on the development of an effective mechanism for managing business processes, taking into account resource capabilities and limitations, which allows the company and its organizations to move to a new level of quality.

In order to evaluate the innovative activity of the enterprises and organizations of the Republic of Uzbekistan and their innovative competitiveness, based on foreign practical experience, innovative development indicators (indicators) are used. Today, the economy of the republic innovative development in the conditions of globalization of diet development indicators can be divided into the following groups:

- cost indicators;
- time indicators;
- update indicators;
- content indicators.

Cost indicators of innovative development are:

1. The value of scientific research costs in trade, which describe the production of high-tech products of the enterprise.
2. Go to buy licenses, patents, “know-how” .gan cost value.

3. The value of the costs incurred by enterprises and organizations to purchase innovations.

4. The value of expenses incurred for the development of initiative developments.

V. CONCLUSION / RECOMMENDATIONS

When concluding time indicators describing innovation processes in terms of time dynamics:

1. Duration of the new product (new technologies) development process (how long the innovative development was created, day, month, year).

2. The duration period of preparation for the production of a new product.

3. The duration of the new product production cycle (time, days, months, years) for the complete production of a product.

Update indicators:

1. The number of new goods and products developed in technological innovations and their implementation.

2. Indicators of the dynamics of updating the product composition (weight of the updated product) (the relative weight of the manufactured product in 2, 3, 5 and 10 years).

3. Acquired (given freely), new technologies (technological advances).

4. The volume of exported innovative products (regarding value and nature).

5. The volume of new services provided (regarding value and nature).

Content indicators:

1. The composition and number of scientific research and other scientific and technical departments (including the number of experimental design bureaus, experimental and testing complexes).

2. Composition of joint ventures involved in the use of new technologies and creation of new products, etc.

3. The number and composition of employees engaged in scientific research.

4. The number and composition of creative initiatives of temporary teams, groups.

Each of the above indicators makes it possible to measure all parameters of innovative processes in the enterprise comprehensively and to correctly assess its weight and place in the development of the economy.

References.

- [1] Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 27, 2018 “On measures to further improve the system of practical implementation of innovative ideas, technologies and projects” No. PQ-3682;
- [2] Perez, Carlota (2002). [Technological Revolutions and Financial Capital: The Dynamics of Bubbles and Golden Ages](#). UK: Edward Elgar Publishing Limited. [ISBN978-1-84376-331-4](#);
- [3] Mirzaev, K. (2011). Approaches and issues for developing livestock services in Uzbekistan. *Perspectives of Innovations, Economics and Business, PIEB*, 8(2), 23-25;
- [4] Ortik E., Khurshida K., Askar D. Theoretical Aspects of Innovations and Investments in Increasing Economic Efficiency // *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*. – 2020. – T. 7. – №. 2. – C. 2020;
- [5] Mirzaev, K.J., & Rahimov, Z.K. (2020). CLUSTERING OF AGRO SERVICE. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), pp 731-736;
- [6] Kudratov, G. Kh., & Mirzaev, K. J. (2010). “Economic problems of the agricultural sector and directions for the development of agricultural services.” Monograph;
- [7] Mirzaev, K. J. (2014). Diversification agroservice to Uzbekistan. *Economics and entrepreneurship*, (1-2), pp 130-132;
- [8] Mirzaev, K., & Janzakov, B. (2020). The determinants of international tourism (in the example of CIS countries). *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(2), 2020;

- [9] Jamankulova, F.E., & Nizomov, M.Q. (2020). The Notion Of Information And Its Significance In The State Economy. CUTTING EDGE-SCIENCE, 20;
- [10] Jomonkulova, F.E., Nizomov, M.Q., & Uralov, S.A. (2020). TO MAKE RADICAL CHANGES IN THE SYSTEM OF HIGHER EDUCATION FOR THE TRAINING OF QUALIFIED PERSONNEL. In Colloquium-journal (No. 29-2, pp. 13-14);
- [11] Jomonkulova, F.E., Tojiyev, N.S., Nizomov, M.Q., & Uralov, S.A. (2020). THE CONCEPT OF INFORMATIZATION AND ITS ROLE IN THE ECONOMY OF THE COUNTRY. In Colloquium-journal (No. 29-1, pp. 60-61).